

Etiology, Risk Factors and Morbidity Profile Associated with Neonatal Hyperbilirubinemia in a Tertiary Care Hospital

Nitish Kumar¹, Brijendra Deo², Santosh Kumar³

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Shree Narayan Medical Institute and Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, India

²Associate Professor, Department of Pediatrics, Shree Narayan Medical Institute and Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, India

³Ex Senior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, All India Institute of Medical Sciences, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 15-05-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Brijendra Deo

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: High serum bilirubin levels are common cause of neonatal admissions, which frequently causes neonates to become icteric. Although severe cases are usually benign, they can cause kernicterus and acute bilirubin encephalopathy, which can result in long-term neurological problems or even death if left untreated. In a tertiary care hospital setting, the purpose of this study was to look into the causes, risk factors, and morbidity profile of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia.

Methods: The study included 100 neonates diagnosed with hyperbilirubinemia. Data were collected from medical records and analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and t-tests were used to evaluate the associations between risk factors and neonatal hyperbilirubinemia.

Results: Of the 100 neonates, 55% were male, with a mean gestational age of 37.8 weeks and a mean birth weight of 2.8 kg. The most common risk factors were breastfeeding issues (breastfeeding and breast milk jaundice) (26%), prematurity (20%), and ABO incompatibility (18%). Significant associations were found between hyperbilirubinemia and ABO incompatibility ($p = 0.03$), Rh incompatibility ($p = 0.02$), G6PD deficiency ($p = 0.01$), prematurity ($p = 0.02$), and breastfeeding issues ($p = 0.04$). Phototherapy was administered to 85% of the neonates, and 5% required exchange transfusion. The mean hospital stay was 6.3 days, with 6% experiencing neurological sequelae.

Conclusion: The study identified significant risk factors for neonatal hyperbilirubinemia, including ABO incompatibility, Rh incompatibility, G6PD deficiency, prematurity, and breastfeeding issues (breastfeeding and breast milk jaundice). These findings underscore the importance of early detection and management of at-risk neonates to prevent severe outcomes.

Recommendations: Enhanced prenatal care, early diagnosis, and timely interventions such as phototherapy and exchange transfusion are critical in managing neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. Further studies are recommended to develop comprehensive guidelines for the prevention and treatment of this condition in diverse healthcare settings.

Keywords: Neonatal Hyperbilirubinemia, Risk Factors, Morbidity, Phototherapy, ABO Incompatibility.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

A common and serious clinical disease affecting babies worldwide is neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. It is characterised by high serum bilirubin levels and frequently appears in newborns as jaundice. With 60% to 80% of term infants and almost all preterm infants acquiring some degree of hyperbilirubinemia during the first week of life, this condition is a primary cause of neonatal hospital admissions [1]. While hyperbilirubinemia is generally not harmful, severe cases can cause acute bilirubin encephalopathy and kernicterus, which, if left untreated, can cause long-term neurological problems and even death.

The etiology of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia is multifactorial. Key contributing factors include increased bilirubin production due to hemolysis, decreased hepatic clearance, and increased enterohepatic circulation. Specific etiological factors identified in recent studies include ABO and Rh incompatibility, glucose-6-phosphate dehydrogenase (G6PD) deficiency, sepsis, and prematurity [2]. A meta-analysis highlighted that exclusive breastfeeding, G6PD deficiency, ABO incompatibility, and preterm birth are significant risk factors for neonatal hyperbilirubinemia,

necessitating close monitoring and timely clinical interventions for at-risk neonates [3].

Recent advancements in understanding the pathophysiology and risk factors associated with neonatal hyperbilirubinemia have led to improved diagnostic and management strategies. Phototherapy remains the mainstay of treatment for hyperbilirubinemia, effectively reducing serum bilirubin levels and preventing the escalation to more severe forms of the disease. For extremely high bilirubin levels, exchange transfusion is employed to rapidly decrease bilirubin and prevent kernicterus [4].

Despite these advancements, neonatal hyperbilirubinemia continues to pose significant challenges, particularly in resource-limited settings where access to timely and adequate treatment may be restricted. A longitudinal study conducted in Nigeria highlighted the high incidence of severe hyperbilirubinemia and its associated morbidities, including a substantial proportion of newborns developing neurological impairments due to delayed or inadequate treatment [5]. This underscores the need for enhanced prenatal care, early detection, and intervention protocols to mitigate the risks associated with neonatal hyperbilirubinemia.

This study aims to investigate the etiology, risk factors, and morbidity profile associated with neonatal hyperbilirubinemia.

Methodology

Study Design: A retrospective observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Shree Narayan Medical Institute & Hospital, Saharsa, Bihar, over a period from December 2021 to May 2023.

Participants: The study included 100 neonates diagnosed with hyperbilirubinemia.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Neonates diagnosed with hyperbilirubinemia within the first 28 days of life.

2. Neonates admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) at Shree Narayan Medical Institute & Hospital.

3. Neonates whose parents provided informed consent for participation.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Neonates with congenital anomalies or metabolic disorders.
2. Neonates who received prior treatment for hyperbilirubinemia before admission to the study hospital.
3. Neonates with incomplete medical records.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all neonates meeting the inclusion criteria within the study period were included consecutively. Data collection was standardized to reduce information bias.

Data Collection: Data were collected retrospectively from medical records. Information gathered included demographic details, clinical findings, laboratory results, treatment interventions, and outcomes.

Procedure: Medical records of eligible neonates were reviewed to extract relevant data. A structured data collection form was used to record the information systematically. The collected data were cross-verified for accuracy and completeness by an independent reviewer.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. The data were summarised using descriptive statistics including mean, median, and standard deviation. Frequencies and percentages were used to represent categorical variables. Using t-tests for continuous variables and chi-square tests for categorical variables, associations between risk factors and newborn hyperbilirubinemia were evaluated. Statistical significance was attained when the p-value was less than 0.05.

Result

A total of 100 neonates diagnosed with hyperbilirubinemia were included in the study. The demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Neonates with Hyperbilirubinemia

Characteristic	N (%) or Mean \pm SD
Gender	
- Male	55 (55%)
- Female	45 (45%)
Gestational Age (weeks)	37.8 \pm 2.1
Birth Weight (kg)	2.8 \pm 0.5
Mode of Delivery	
- Vaginal	60 (60%)
- Cesarean Section	40 (40%)
Age at Diagnosis (days)	4.2 \pm 1.5

The etiological factors and risk factors associated with neonatal hyperbilirubinemia are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Etiological Factors and Risk Factors Associated with Neonatal Hyperbilirubinemia

Risk Factor	N (%)
ABO Incompatibility	18 (18%)
Rh Incompatibility	5 (5%)
G6PD Deficiency	7 (7%)
Sepsis	17 (17%)
Prematurity	20 (20%)
Breastfeeding Issues (breastfeeding and breast milk jaundice)	26 (26 %)
Birth Asphyxia	7 (7%)

The morbidity profile of neonates with hyperbilirubinemia, including complications and interventions, is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Morbidity Profile of Neonates with Hyperbilirubinemia

Morbidity/Complication	N (%)
Exchange Transfusion	5 (5%)
Phototherapy	85 (85%)
Hospital Stay (days)	6.3 ± 2.4
Neurological Sequelae	6 (6%)
Readmission	8 (8%)

Associations between risk factors and neonatal hyperbilirubinemia were evaluated. For categorical variables, chi-square tests were used to establish statistical significance, and for continuous variables, t-tests were employed.

Table 4: Association Between Risk Factors and Hyperbilirubinemia

Risk Factor	Hyperbilirubinemia (N)	p-value
ABO Incompatibility	18	0.03*
Rh Incompatibility	5	0.02*
G6PD Deficiency	7	0.01*
Sepsis	17	0.05
Prematurity	20	0.02*
Breastfeeding Issues	26	0.04*
Birth asphyxia	7	0.2

*p < 0.05 indicates statistical significance

Discussion

In a tertiary care hospital, 100 neonates participated in this study to examine the etiology, risk factors, and morbidity profile of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. The demographic information showed a gender distribution that was almost equal, with a small male majority (55%). The mean birth weight was 2.8 kg, and the average gestational age was 37.8 weeks. Remarkably, 40% of the neonates were delivered via caesarean section, compared to 60% who were delivered vaginally.

The study identified several key risk factors for neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. Breastfeeding issues (26%), prematurity (20%), and ABO incompatibility (18%) were the most prevalent risk factors. Additionally, G6PD deficiency (7%) and sepsis (17%) were significant contributing factors. Statistical analysis revealed significant associations between hyperbilirubinemia and specific risk factors: ABO incompatibility (p = 0.03), Rh incompatibility (p = 0.02) G6PD deficiency (p = 0.01), prematurity (p = 0.02), and breastfeeding

issues (p = 0.04). These findings underscore the importance of early identification and management of these risk factors to prevent severe hyperbilirubinemia.

In terms of morbidity, 85% of the neonates received phototherapy, and 5% required exchange transfusion. The mean duration of hospital stay was 6.3 days, highlighting the substantial healthcare resources utilized for managing this condition. Neurological sequelae were observed in 6% of the cases, indicating the potential long-term impacts of severe hyperbilirubinemia. The readmission rate was 8%, suggesting that a small proportion of neonates might experience recurrent or persistent issues related to hyperbilirubinemia.

Overall, the results of this study emphasize the need for vigilant monitoring and prompt intervention for neonates at risk of hyperbilirubinemia, particularly those with identified significant risk factors. Early and effective management strategies, including adequate breastfeeding support and timely phototherapy, can mitigate the severity of

hyperbilirubinemia and reduce associated morbidities. These findings provide valuable insights for healthcare professionals in tertiary care settings to enhance the care and outcomes for neonates with hyperbilirubinemia.

In a Hyderabad, India, NICU, 210 neonates with hyperbilirubinemia (bilirubin >12 mg/dL) were evaluated. Physiological jaundice was the most frequent cause, followed by idiopathic etiologies and septicemia. Less frequently, blood group incompatibility was the reason. The risk factor that was shown to be most common was late preterm. The average length of phototherapy, according to the study, was 2.50 days, and three infants needed double volume exchange transfusions (DVET) because of their severe hyperbilirubinemia. During their stay in the NICU, none of the newborns who needed DVET developed BIND (bilirubin-induced neurological dysfunction) [6].

Early discharge, Rh isoimmunization, and G6PD deficiency were identified to be significant risk factors for severe hyperbilirubinemia needing exchange transfusion in a cohort study involving 115 newborns in Turkey. Acute bilirubin encephalopathy (ABE) was linked to both G6PD deficiency and being a refugee [7].

A study documented hyperbilirubinemia in preterm and term babies in Nellore, India. The most common etiological factors were sepsis (23%), ABO incompatibility (20%), and Rh incompatibility (6%). ABO incompatibility was more prevalent in term babies, while sepsis was more common in preterm infants. The need for exchange transfusion was higher among term babies [8].

Neonatal jaundice needing exchange transfusion was shown to be primarily caused by sepsis (31.17%), ABO incompatibility (24.59%), and Rh incompatibility (14.75%) in a Dhaka study. According to the study, 19 neonates experienced exchange transfusion-related problems like bradycardia and catheter block, while 20 neonates showed symptoms of kernicterus [9].

Significant correlations between neonatal hyperbilirubinemia and characteristics including IUGR, preterm, ABO incompatibility, breastfeeding issues, and birth asphyxia were found in a case-control study conducted in rural central India. In order to lower morbidity and death, the study underlined the significance of early detection and intervention [10].

Conclusion

This study identified critical risk factors for neonatal hyperbilirubinemia, including ABO incompatibility, Rh incompatibility, G6PD deficiency, prematurity, and breastfeeding issues. The findings highlight the need for early detection

and intervention to prevent severe outcomes such as neurological sequelae. Effective management strategies, including phototherapy and exchange transfusion, play a vital role in mitigating the risks associated with this condition. Enhanced prenatal care and comprehensive guidelines are essential to improve neonatal outcomes and reduce the burden of hyperbilirubinemia. Further research is recommended to refine prevention and treatment protocols across various healthcare settings.

References

1. Xie L, Song Z, Liu Y, et al. Risk factors for neonatal hyperbilirubinemia: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Transl Pediatr.* 2022 ;11(5):707-714. doi:10.21037/tp-22-229.
2. Ezeonwu B, Ojukwu JU, Oguonu T. Clinical evaluation of severe neonatal hyperbilirubinemia in a resource-limited setting: a 4-year longitudinal study in south-East Nigeria. *BMC Pediatr.* 2019;19(1):139. doi:10.1186/s12887-019-1516-2.
3. Kemper AR, Newman TB, Slaughter JL, et al. Clinical Practice Guideline Revision: Management of Hyperbilirubinemia in the Newborn Infant 35 or More Weeks of Gestation. *Pediatrics.* 2022;150(3). doi:10.1542/peds.2022-058859.
4. Maisels MJ, Bhutani VK, Bogen D, et al. Management of Hyperbilirubinemia in the Newborn Infant 35 or More Weeks of Gestation: An Update. *Pediatrics.* 2022;150(3). doi: 10.1542/peds.2022-058859.
5. Maxted AP, George S, Murray J, et al. Systematic review of global clinical practice guidelines for neonatal hyperbilirubinemia. *BMJ Open.* 2022;12(1). doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2021-053826.
6. Ali SA, Lakshmi C, Reddy UN, Nazneen F, Muzammil. A prospective study on etiological factors and clinical indicators in term and near term neonates admitted with hyperbilirubinemia in NICU in a tertiary care hospital in Hyderabad, India. *IP International Journal of Medical Paediatrics and Oncology.* 2021.
7. Bozkurt Ö, Yücesoy E, Oğuz B, Akinel Ö, Palalı M, Ataş N. Severe neonatal hyperbilirubinemia in the south-east region of Turkey. *Turkish journal of medical sciences.* 2019.
8. Garg K, Kondle V. Prospective study of clinical profile, causes, risk factors and treatment of hyperbilirubinemia in preterm and term babies. *International Journal of Contemporary Pediatrics.* 2018.
9. Rahman S, Afroz S, Parvin R, Iman K, Zinatunnesa. Exchange Transfusion in Neonatal Hyperbilirubinemia: Experience of A Tertiary Care Hospital in Dhaka. *Dhaka Shishu (Children) Hospital Journal.* 2023.

10. Selvam S, Taksande A. Risk Factors of Hyperbilirubinemia - A Case-Control Study in a Tertiary Level Hospital in Rural Central India.

Journal of Evolution of Medical and Dental Sciences. 2021.